

Research Article

The Sosioemosi@Sekolah Module

Suziyani Mohamed^{1,*}, Salmiah Bujang², Mohd Syazwan Zainal³, and Kamariah Abu Bakar⁴

¹ Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; suziyani@ukm.edu.my; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0855-2497>

² Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; salmiahbujang@ukm.edu.my; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-6247-6589>

³ Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; syazwanzainal@ukm.edu.my; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1450-2760>

⁴ Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia; kamariah_abubakar@ukm.edu.my; ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8134-6182>

* Correspondence: suziyani@ukm.edu.my; +60139987159.

Abstract: Social-emotional skills are a key component of holistic development in all students, including adolescents with Special Educational Needs (SEN). Adolescents with SEN often face greater challenges in managing emotions and social interactions due to their disabilities. Without strong social-emotional skills, they are more vulnerable to psychosocial issues, behavioural difficulties, and lower academic achievement. To address this, the Sosioemosi@Sekolah Module was developed as a practical guide for teachers to deliver targeted social-emotional interventions for SEN adolescents. The module focuses on three integrated components, namely, social-emotional skills, social communication, and self-management, embedded into daily school routines. The development followed the ADDIE Model, which includes five phases: needs analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. In the needs analysis phase, 100 respondents helped identify the required content, approaches, and strategies. Furthermore, in design and development phases, 16 special education teachers and 5 subject matter experts evaluated the module, contributing to its refinement. The module was piloted in a special education classroom. Implementation findings showed positive usability and notable improvement in adolescents' social-emotional competencies, suggesting that integrating these skills into everyday teaching enhances character development, self-regulation, and social interaction. The module also shows commercial potential, with proposed formats including a teacher's guidebook, learning kits, professional development resources, and a digital app. Intellectual property registration is underway through Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, alongside ISBN registration via the National Library of Malaysia. In summary, the Sosioemosi@Sekolah Module offers a promising and practical innovation in special education, aligned with the goals of inclusive education.

Keywords: social-emotional; special education needs; learning disability.

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Social-emotional development refers to an individual's ability to understand and regulate emotions, establish positive interpersonal relationships, develop empathy, and make responsible decisions in social contexts (Denham et al., 2012). These competencies are essential for personal well-being, academic success, and the ability to function effectively in various social environments. Particularly during adolescence, when emotional intensity and peer interaction increase, social-emotional skills become critical for navigating complex social situations and maintaining psychological

resilience (CASEL, 2020). Developing these skills not only supports academic engagement but also contributes to healthier peer relationships, reduced behavioural issues, and long-term mental health outcomes.

However, adolescents with learning disabilities often experience significant challenges in acquiring and applying social-emotional competencies. Due to cognitive processing difficulties, limited communication skills, and frequent experiences of academic failure or social rejection, individuals with learning disabilities are more vulnerable to emotional dysregulation, social withdrawal, and low self-esteem (Humphrey & Wigelsworth, 2016). These difficulties may hinder their ability to form meaningful social connections and cope with everyday stressors, leading to further marginalisation in school and community settings. Given these challenges, it is imperative to intentionally nurture and support the social-emotional development of this population to promote inclusion, independence, and overall quality of life.

In light of these needs, there is a growing demand for structured, evidence-informed teaching modules that can be implemented by teachers to foster social-emotional learning among adolescents with learning disabilities. A well-designed module provides teachers with a consistent framework, age-appropriate strategies, and practical tools to support students' emotional growth and social competence within classroom routines. Furthermore, such resources enhance teachers' confidence and capacity in addressing the diverse emotional and behavioural needs of their students. Therefore, the aim of this study is to develop a structured social-emotional learning module tailored specifically for adolescents with learning disabilities.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study adopted a Design and Development Research (DDR) approach, guided by the ADDIE model, which comprises five key phases: (i) analysis, (ii) design, (iii) development, (iv) implementation, and (v) evaluation. Data collection was structured around these phases. Table 1 presents detailed information on the sampling techniques, participant categories, and the number of participants involved at each phase of the study.

Table 1. Participants Information.

Phase	Sampling Techniques	Participant's Categories	Number of Participants
Phase 1: Analysis	Simple random sampling	Special education teachers	100
Phase 2: Design & Phase 3: Development	Purposive sampling	Special education teachers Experts	16 5
Phase 4: Implementation	Purposive sampling	Special education teacher Adolescents with learning disability	1 5
Phase 5: Evaluation	Random sampling	Special education teachers	30

2.1 Instrument

A total of four instruments were employed in this study, each adapted from established research. Table 2 outlines the instruments used at the respective phases of the study in detail.

Table 2. Instruments Information.

Phase	Instruments	Number of Item	Scoring
Phase 1: Analysis	Needs analysis survey <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section A: Demography information • Section B: Teachers' competency • Section C: Needs of the module • Section D: Features of the module 	30	4-point likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree
Phase 2: Design & Phase 3: Development	Expert validation questionnaire <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section A: Demography information • Section B: Module objectives • Section C: Presentation of the module • Section D: Design of the module • Section E: Component of the module • Section F: Content of the module 	47	7-point likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree
Phase 4: Implementation	Semi-structured interview <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feasibility of the module • Constraint • Suggestion for improvement 	11	-
Phase 5: Evaluation	Usability questionnaire <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Section A: Demography information • Section B: Ease of use • Section C: Content appropriateness • Section D: Instructional clarity • Section E: Engagement potential • Section F: Pedagogical value • Section G: Adaptability • Section H: Satisfaction 	48	4-point likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree

2.2 Data Collection and Analysis

Table 3 presents a comprehensive outline of the data collection and analysis procedures implemented at each phase of the study.

Table 3. Data Collection and Analysis Information.

Phase	Data Collection Procedure	Data Analysis Procedure
Phase 1: Analysis	Survey	Descriptive analysis
Phase 2: Design & Phase 3: Development	Survey	Fuzzy Delphi
Phase 4: Implementation	Focus group discussion	Thematic analysis
Phase 5: Evaluation	Interview	Thematic analysis
Phase 5: Evaluation	Survey	Descriptive analysis

3. FINDINGS

The findings of this study are presented in accordance with the respective phases of the research.

3.1 Phase 1: Needs Analysis Survey

This study involved special education teachers with a range of ages, qualifications, and teaching experience. In terms of age, 30% of respondents were between 26 and 30 years old, 17% were aged 31 to 35, and 53% of respondents were 36 years old and above. Most participants (85%) held a bachelor's degree, while 15% had a master's degree. Regarding teaching experience in special education, 44% had 1 to 5 years of experience, 11% had 6 to 10 years, 13% had 11 to 15 years, 21% had

16 to 20 years, and 11% had more than 21 years of experience. Table 4 presents the descriptive analysis findings for the dimensions measured in this phase of the study.

Table 4. Descriptive Analysis Findings of Needs Analysis Survey.

Sections	M	SD	Score Mean Interpretation
Section B: Teachers' competency	3.01	0.453	Moderate-high
Section C: Needs of the module	3.98	0.380	High
Section D: Features of the module	3.98	0.431	High

3.2. Phase 2: Design & Phase 3: Development

A total of 21 experts, comprising special education teachers and university lecturers, were appointed to evaluate the module. These experts were responsible for verifying, validating, and rating the content to ensure its relevance and quality. Table 5 presents the findings of the Fuzzy Delphi analysis conducted for the module.

Table 5. Fuzzy Delphi Analysis Findings.

Sections	Threshold Value (d)	Expert Consensus (%)	Fuzzy Score	Expert Consensus
Section B: Module objectives	0.025	100%	0.939	Accepted
Section C: Presentation of the module	0.000	100%	0.948	Accepted
Section D: Design of the module	0.000	100%	0.948	Accepted
Section E: Component of the module	0.045	100%	0.900	Accepted
Section F: Content of the module	0.127	100%	0.967	Accepted

3.3 Phase 3: Implementation

The module was implemented by teachers over a period of 14 weeks. Following the implementation, one-to-one interviews were conducted to gather their feedback. Participant reported that the module significantly enhanced their understanding of social-emotional development and improved their ability to recognise social-emotional skills in students' daily experiences. Furthermore, the module was found to be helpful in guiding the nurturing of these skills through routine classroom activities. However, the participant also offered several suggestions for improvement, including the need for a teacher's manual that provides clear guidance on how to adapt activity steps and modify learning materials to accommodate diverse student needs.

3.4 Phase 4: Evaluation

A total of 30 special education teachers participated in providing feedback on the module's usability. The results of the usability analysis are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Descriptive Analysis Findings of Usability.

Sections	M	SD	Score Mean Interpretation
Section B: Ease of use	3.82	0.536	High
Section C: Content appropriateness	3.88	0.490	High
Section D: Instructional clarity	3.60	0.480	High
Section E: Engagement potential	3.90	0.530	High
Section F: Pedagogical value	3.90	0.485	High
Section G: Adaptability	3.71	0.390	High
Section H: Satisfaction	3.90	0.481	High

4. DISCUSSION

The findings from this study provide meaningful contributions to the field of special education, particularly in supporting teachers who work with adolescents with learning disabilities. The needs analysis highlighted a clear demand among special education teachers for structured resources to enhance their capacity in delivering social-emotional learning. Teachers expressed a strong interest in having a dedicated module to guide their instruction, suggesting that current classroom practices may lack sufficient tools to effectively support the development of social-emotional skills. The high ratings of module relevance and desired features indicate that such a resource could help bridge the gap between theoretical understanding and classroom application. With many teachers possessing extensive experience and training, a structured, evidence-based module not only enhances their professional practice but also supports consistent, purposeful instruction aligned with inclusive education goals.

Furthermore, the expert validation and positive usability feedback confirm that the module is well-designed and practically applicable. Teachers reported increased confidence in identifying and nurturing social-emotional development through daily routines, which is essential for fostering self-awareness, emotional regulation, and interpersonal skills among students with learning disabilities. These skills are foundational to improving long-term educational and social outcomes. The module's potential to be adapted to various learning contexts adds further value, allowing teachers to tailor instruction to meet diverse student needs. Importantly, the study highlights the necessity of providing educators with not just knowledge, but also practical tools and strategies that can be seamlessly integrated into their teaching. As such, the developed module stands as a promising contribution to improving classroom practices and supporting the holistic development of learners with special educational needs.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development of a Sosioemosi@Sekolah Module for adolescents with learning disabilities offers a valuable contribution to special education practice. Grounded in the needs and insights of experienced educators and validated by expert consensus, the module provides practical guidance for fostering essential social-emotional skills through daily classroom routines. Its usability and relevance, as reflected in teacher feedback, demonstrate its potential to enhance instructional quality and promote positive developmental outcomes for learners with diverse needs. By equipping teachers with a purposeful and adaptable tool, this study supports the broader aim of inclusive education and highlights the importance of empowering educators to address the holistic needs of students with learning disabilities.

Acknowledgments: This study supported by research grant GG-2024-068.

References

- CASEL. (2020). *What is SEL?* Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning.
- Denham, S. A., Bassett, H. H., Zinsser, K., & Wyatt, T. (2012). How preschoolers' social-emotional learning predicts their early school success: Developing theory-promoting, competency-based assessments. *Infant and Child Development, 21*(6), 667–706.
- Humphrey, N., & Wigelsworth, M. (2016). Social and emotional learning: A critical appraisal of the evidence base. *British Journal of Educational Psychology, 86*(3), 370–390.